

Contribution of Muthulakshmi Reddy in Women Empowerment

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Abstract

Dr. Muthu Lakshmi Reddy was an eminent medical practioners, social reformer and legislator. She sacrificed her life for development of women. Contribution of Dr. Muthu Lakshmi Reddy to the upliftment of women and children went ahead with her noble work. Her scope of activities was very wide and she tried to tackle various problems of women like their backwardness, illiteracy, ill-health and also the welfare of children and medicinal relief of the poor. She was a legend into herself.

Introduction

Woman’s Emancipation in India started with great zeal in the early decades of the nineteenth century. Dr. Muthu Lakshmi Reddy became the first woman house surgeon in the government maternity and ophthalmic hospital madras. She was a pioneer in the fight for social and political upliftment of women in India. Especially the legislation to abolish Devadasi system that was widely prevalent in parts of Tamil Nadu and other parts of south India. By her multifaceted activities. She showed that women could be better than men. Dr. Muthu Lakshmi Reddy hailed from a socially handicapped environment in an era. When girls were born only to be married. She was born in 1886 in the small princely state of Pudukottai. She was the first women medicinal graduate of Madras University in 1912 and become the first Indian women member of a legislative council in 1927. She was the first female student in a men’s college. She became the first women house surgeon in the government maternity and ophthalmic hospital, Madras.

Raising of Dr. Muthu Lakshmi Reddy

Dr. Muthu Lakshmi Reddy was born in 1886 in the small princely state of Pudukottai of Tamil Nadu. In spite of various constraints faced by girls. In India of her time she could complete her higher education and was admitted into medicinal profession. In 1907 she joined Madras Medicinal College. Where she achieved a brilliant academic record. The principal thought that she might demoralize the male students.

The enlightened maharaja of Pudukottai ignored these objections admitted her to Meris College and he gave her scholarship. Dr. Muthu Lakshmi Reddy then enrolled in Madras College for MBBS where

she received gold medal for her academic excellence. She did her higher practice of medicine to take up a request from the “Women’s Indian Association” (WIA) and entered the Madras legislative council. She married a doctor called Sundara Reddy in 1914 under condition that he should always treat her as an equal and he should never stop her for pursuing her dreams. She was an eminent medicinal practitioner social reforms and legislator. She is also the founder of the Adyar cancer Institute.

Carrier & Social Reforms

- Dr. Muthu Lakshmi Reddy led the agitation for municipal and legislative franchise for women. She was concerned about the orphans especially girls. She arranged for them free boarding and lodging and started the Avvai home in Chennai. Dr. Muthu Lakshmi Reddy was the numerous social reforms her book “My Experience as a legislator” records all her services in the legislature.
- In 1893 an appeal was put forth by the Madras Hindu reform Association to put an end to the performance of Devadasi at public and private functions. In support of the resolution, she met and interviewed several hundred Devadasi across the Madras Presidency. The Madras Legislative Assembly in the December of 1947, she passed the bill for the suppression of brothels and immortal trafficking in women and children. A home for rescued girls and she opened through her efforts a hostel for Muslims girls and given scholarships for marriage be raised.

Emancipation of Women

Freedom is the birth right of every human being every beasts and birds. All lives thrive best when they are free. Freedom and responsibility bring out the best from the individual and the race. The emancipation of women has always been closely bound up with the struggle for political freedom. The women’s Indian Association founded in 1917 in Madras was the premier women’s organization which bonded together for their self-development and for the service of others Mrs. Cousin with Dr. Annie Besant and Srimathi Sarojini Naidu led the deputation to Mr. Montagu during his visit to India demanding franchise for women’s organization like the Women’s Indian Association and the A.I.W.C., which prepared women to share with men in all the ordeals of public life. Women are in the front in every fields. Indian women have a great role to play in the modern world with us chaos and rumblings of another war with their background of philosophy and religious with their apprenticeship under Gandhian leadership with the sense of mother hood strong in them they can be and should be the ambassadors of love, peace and unity.

Political Contributions

History has stood witness to the brilliance of women in politics, time and again. Women across the world has often held the political scepter firmly in their hands when ever needed. India has also seen such influential female political figures from time to time. Their schemes and political traits have been appreciated by many and criticized by many more. However, their contribution to the development of the country can never be over looked. In India, reform movements before and after Independence they have achieved an unprecedented political break through with the reservation of seats for them in panchayats and other public bodies. It is heartening to note that Indian women were among the earliest to get their political rights (Right to vote) without any political movement like die unity in states and many western countries. They were among the foremost to take active part in politics eve in pre-independence times. The role of women in India politics witnessed in ancient India widened more in British India. Anni Besant through was not an Indian but become the first women president of Indian National Congress (INC) in 1915. In 1916 she launched a home rule movement of fight for Indian and actively participated in Indian Independence Movement.

Then there was Sarojini Naidu who be the president of INC in 1925 Dr. Muthu Lakshmi Reddy was nominated by Sakthi Hari Haran to the legislature as a member of the legislative council in 1926, and become the first women to be a member of any legislature in India. When she was elected as a deputy chairperson of the legislative council. She became the first women in the world to become the vice president of a legislature. She was the prime mover behind the legislation that abolished the Devadasi system and played a keen role in raising the minimum marriage age for women in India in 1930 ,she resigned from the madras legislature as a protest following the imprisonment of Mahatma Gandhi .She argued for the removal of the Devadasi system that was widely prevalent in Tamil Nadu at that time against stiff resistance from the congress lobby led by Sathya Moorthy Aiyar. She was the founder president of the Women’s Indian Association (WIA) and become the first older women of the Madras Corporation. Dr. Muthu Lakshmi Reddy was actively involve the setting up of several toilets and women’s toilets and initiated measure to improve the medicinal facilities given to slum dwellers. In 1930, she founded Avvai, a home for destitute woman and orphans of Besant Avenue, Adyar as an MLC, she introduced a scheme of free education for girls up to class sight.

Awards and Achievements

Dr. Muthu Lakshmi Reddy continued to fight for her cause till the end of her days and never let any things come in her day’s ways. Even at the age of 80 she was energetic and vibrant. Her human preoccupation took her away from politics and she stuck her mission in Gandhian ways. She received the Padma Bhusan award by the president of India in 1956. Her two outstanding monuments gifts for humanity remain the Avvai home (for children) and the cancer Institute. Her book named “My Experience as a Legislator” recounts her initiatives in respect of social reform taken by her in the madras legislature. Government of India conferred on her Padma Bhusan in 1956 in recognition of her meritorious services to the nation. Dr. Muthu Lakshmi Reddy was an impressive woman who worked her way through a biased system which treated woman as second class citizens.

Conclusion

Dr. Muthu Lakshmi Reddy dedicated her life for the society. She fought for purity in public life. Her scope of activities was very wide and she tried to tackle various problems of women like their backwardness, illiteracy, and ill-health, social economic legal and political discrimination and also the welfare of children and medical relief to the poor. Dr. Muthu Lakshmi Reddy trained a large number of social workers to carry on the work she left behind her. She was a legend into herself. Contribution of Dr. Muthu Lakshmi Reddy to the upliftment of women and children especially the under privileged was duly recognized in 1947 with the raising of the first National flag at Red fort which carried her named. Dr.Reddy and Dr.Sarojini Naidu we would not be occupying the high positions that we do today.Dr. Muthu Lakshmi Reddy the pioneer in the fight for social and political uplift of women of India.Dr. Muthu Lakshmi Reddy was the president of the woman’s India Association for over 30 years.Dr. Muthu Lakshmi Reddy passed away on 22nd July 1968. We thank god for the full life. She lived for the dedication and sincerity with which she served her fellow men and her country may her soul rest in peace.

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